
A DFT Study of the Relationships between Electronic Structure and Central Benzodiazepine Receptor Affinity in a group of Imidazo[1,5-*a*]quinoline derivatives and a group of 3-Substituted 6-Phenyl-4*H*-imidazo[1,5-*a*]-[1,4]benzodiazepines and related compounds

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Abstract We have analyzed the relationships between electronic structure and central benzodiazepine receptor affinity of the title compounds. The electronic structure was obtained at the B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) level after full geometry optimization. Statistically significant relationships were obtained for both groups of molecules. The corresponding partial 2D-pharmacophores were built. They could be used for the design of molecules with improved affinity.

Keywords Benzodiazepines, KPG method, DFT, QSAR, SAR, receptor affinity

Introduction

GABA_A receptors are the main inhibitory neurotransmitter receptors in mammalian brain. This receptor is a ligand-gated ion channel of the Cys-loop family that includes the 5-HT₃, nicotinic acetylcholine and strychnine-sensitive glycine receptors. Its endogenous ligand is the γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA). Besides GABA, the active site also binds drugs such as gabaxadol, muscimol and bicuculline. The receptor also contains a number of different allosteric binding sites which modulate indirectly its activity. These sites are the targets of several other drugs such as the neuroactive steroids, ethanol, benzodiazepines (BZ), nonbenzodiazepines, barbiturates, inhaled anesthetics and picrotoxin. BZs bind to distinct benzodiazepine binding sites (central benzodiazepine receptors, CBR) situated at the interface between the α - and γ -subunits of α - and γ -subunit having GABA_A receptors. When bound, the BZ locks the GABA_A receptor into a conformation where the neurotransmitter GABA has much higher affinity for the GABA_A receptor. This increases the frequency of opening of the associated chloride ion channel and hyperpolarizes the membrane. The final effect is a potentiation of the inhibitory effect of the available GABA leading to sedative and anxiolytic effects. Benzodiazepines are one of the pharmaceutical industry's top-selling families of prescription drugs: diazepam, alprazolam, chlordiazepoxide, clorazepate, clonazepam, oxazepam, triazolam, lorazepam, flunitrazepam, etc., are almost worldwide known and used. This has propelled the research on these molecules in search of more active and less addictive compounds (and, undoubtedly, of a patent) [1-15].

Time ago we carried out a DFT study of the relationships between electronic structure and peripheral benzodiazepine receptor affinity in a group of N,N-dialkyl-2-phenylindol-3-ylglyoxylamides [16]. From that year the method employed underwent a series of theoretical advances that are of enough importance to be tested in different molecular systems having different biological activities. As BZs are important molecular systems, we

present in this paper the results of a theoretical study of the relationships between electronic structure and central benzodiazepine receptor affinity in a group of imidazo[1,5-*a*]quinoline derivatives and another group of 3-substituted 6-phenyl-4*H*-imidazo[1,5-*a*]-[1,4]benzodiazepines.

Methods, models and calculations

The technique employed to get structure-activity relationships is the Klopman-Peradejordi-Gómez (KPG) method. Briefly, the KPG method describes the reactivity of a given atom by twenty reactivity indices plus the orientational parameter of the substituent(s) if needed. As a recent full review of the method has been published[17], we refer the reader to it and to some other publications (see below for atom selection)[18-27]. The KPG method has produced excellent results for a variety of molecular systems and biological activities (see [28-44] and references therein). For these reasons we shall discuss only the results. The molecules were selected from two publications of the same research group [4, 45]. The data employed for our analysis corresponds to the inhibition of [³H] Flumazenil specific binding to CBR in bovine cortical membranes (reported as K_i , in nM). The data of the two articles was kept separated and named Group A and group B (see Figs. 1 and 2 and Tables 1 and 2).

Figure 1: General structure of molecules of Group A

Table 1: Structure and biological activity of Group A

Molecule	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	log (K _i)
1	C ₂ H ₅	N(CH ₃) ₂	H	H	0.91
2	C(CH ₃) ₃	N(CH ₃) ₂	H	H	1.04
3	C ₂ H ₅	N(CH ₃) <i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	H	H	0.28
4	C(CH ₃) ₃	N(CH ₃) <i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	H	H	0.25
5	C ₂ H ₅	N(<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇) ₂	H	H	-0.04
6	C(CH ₃) ₃	N(<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇) ₂	H	H	0.08
7	C ₂ H ₅	N(CH ₃)CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	H	H	1.30
8	C(CH ₃) ₃	N(CH ₃)CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	H	H	1.15
9	C ₂ H ₅	N(C ₂ H ₄) ₂ NCH ₃	H	H	1.74
10	C ₂ H ₅	OC(CH ₃) ₃	H	CH ₃	0
11	C ₂ H ₅	N(<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇) ₂	H	CH ₃	0.18
12	C(CH ₃) ₃	N(<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇) ₂	H	CH ₃	0
13	C ₂ H ₅	N(CH ₃)CH ₂ CCH	H	CH ₃	0.08
14	C ₂ H ₅	N(CH ₃)CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	H	CH ₃	0.81
15	C(CH ₃) ₃	N(CH ₃)CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	H	CH ₃	0.41
16	C ₂ H ₅	N(<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇) ₂	H	C ₂ H ₅	0.40
17	C(CH ₃) ₃	N(<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇) ₂	H	C ₂ H ₅	0.75
18	C ₂ H ₅	N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	H	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	2.23
19	C(CH ₃) ₃	N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	H	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	3.46
20	C ₂ H ₅	N(<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇) ₂	H	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	1.53
21	C(CH ₃) ₃	N(<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇) ₂	H	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	3.16
22	C ₂ H ₅	N(<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇) ₂	F	H	-0.36
23	C ₂ H ₅	N(CH ₃)CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	F	H	0.76

Figure 2: General structure of molecules of Group B

Table 2: Structure and biological activity of Group B

Molecule	R	R ₁	R ₂	Ar	log(K _i)
1	COOEt	H	H	<i>p</i> -fluorophenyl	1.06
2	COOEt	H	H	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	1.10
3	COOEt	H	H	<i>p</i> -methylphenyl	1.06
4	COOEt	H	H	<i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl	2.04
5	COOEt	F	H	<i>p</i> -fluorophenyl	1.04
6	COOEt	F	H	<i>m</i> -nitrophenyl	0.64
7	COOEt	F	H	<i>p</i> -nitrophenyl	1.17
8	COOEt	Cl	H	<i>p</i> -fluorophenyl	2.27
9	COOEt	Cl	H	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	2.37
10	COOEt	Cl	H	<i>p</i> -methylphenyl	2.30
11	COOEt	Cl	H	<i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl	2.32
12	COOEt	Cl	H	<i>m</i> -nitrophenyl	0.23
13	COOEt	Cl	H	1-naphthyl	2.27
14	COO- <i>t</i> -Bu	Cl	H	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	3.11
15	CN	Cl	H	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	3.22

Calculations

The electronic structure of molecules was obtained within the Density Functional Theory (DFT) at the B3LYP/6-31g(d,p) level after full geometry optimization with the Gaussian software [46]. All the data required to calculate the numerical values of the local atomic reactivity indices was obtained from the Gaussian results file with the D-Cent-QSAR software [47]. All electron populations smaller than or equal to 0.01e were considered as zero [25]. Negative electron populations produced by the Mulliken Population Analysis were corrected [48]. Orientational parameters were calculated as usual [21, 49, 50]. As the resolution of the system of linear equations is not possible because we have not sufficient molecules, we made use of Linear Multiple Regression Analysis (LMRA) techniques to find the best solution. For each case, a matrix containing the dependent variable (log(K_i)) and the local atomic reactivity indices of all atoms of a common skeleton as independent variables was built. The Statistica software was used for LMRA [51]. The *common skeleton approach* holds that there is a definite collection of atoms accounting for nearly all the biological activity. The action of the substituents consists in modifying the electronic structure of the common skeleton and influencing the right position of the drug through the orientational parameters.

Results

Results for Group A

Fig. 3 shows the common skeleton of Group A used for LMRA.

Figure 3: Common skeleton numbering (Group A)

The best equation obtained is:

$$\log(K_i) = 1.41 + 0.007\phi_{R4} + 0.80\mu_{21} + 6.62F_{10}(\text{HOMO}-1)^* + 4.97F_5(\text{HOMO}-2)^* \quad (1)$$

with $n=22$, $R=0.95$, $R^2=0.91$, $\text{adj-}R^2=0.89$, $F(4,17)=43.211$ ($p<0.000001$) and a standard error of estimate of 0.34. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the $\pm 2\sigma$ limits. Here, ϕ_{R4} is the orientational parameter of R_4 (see Fig. 1), μ_{21} is the local atomic electronic chemical potential of atom 21, $F_{10}(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$ is the Fukui index of the second highest occupied MO localized on atom 10 and $F_5(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$ is the Fukui index of the third highest occupied MO localized on atom 5. Tables 3 and 4 show the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of variables and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 1. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 4). Figure 4 displays the plot of observed vs. calculated $\log(K_i)$.

Table 3: Beta coefficients and t-test for significance of variables in Eq. 1

Variable	Beta	t(17)	p-level
ϕ_{R4}	0.88	10.44	0.0000001
μ_{21}	0.57	6.71	0.000004
$F_{10}(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$	0.31	3.94	0.001
$F_5(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$	0.24	3.18	0.006

Table 4: Matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables in Eq. 1

	ϕ_{R4}	μ_{21}	$F_{10}(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$	$F_5(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$
ϕ_{R4}	1.00			
μ_{21}	0.20	1.00		
$F_{10}(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$	0.10	0.14	1.00	
$F_5(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$	0.03	0.00	0.00	1.00

Figure 4: Plot of predicted versus observed $\log(K_i)$ values (Eq. 1). Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval. The associated statistical parameters of Eq. 1 indicate that this equation is statistically significant and that the variation of the numerical values of a group of four local atomic reactivity indices of atoms of the common skeleton

explains about 89% of the variation of $\log(K_i)$. Figure 4, spanning about 4 orders of magnitude, shows that there is a good correlation of observed *versus* calculated values.

Local Molecular Orbitals

Table 5 shows the Local Molecular Orbitals of atom 5, 10 and 21 (see Fig. 3). Nomenclature: Molecule (HOMO) / (HOMO-2)* (HOMO-1)* (HOMO)* - (LUMO)* (LUMO+1)* (LUMO+2)*.

Table 5: Local Molecular Orbitals of atoms 5, 10 and 21

Molecule	Atom 5	Atom 10	Atom 21
1 (82)	79σ80π82π-83π84π85π	80π81σ82π-83π85σ86σ	70σ79σ81σ-95σ96σ97σ
2 (90)	87σ88π90π-91σ92π93π	88π89σ90π-91σ93σ94σ	76σ87σ89σ-103σ104σ105σ
3 (94)	91σ92π94π-95π96π97π	92π93σ94π-95π97π98σ	84σ91σ93σ-106σ107σ108σ
4 (102)	99σ100π102π-103π104π105π	99σ100σ102π-103π105π106σ	92σ99σ101σ-112σ114σ115σ
5 (98)	95π96π98π-99π100π101π	96π97σ98π-99π101π102π	89σ95σ97σ-107σ108σ110σ
6 (106)	103π104π106π-107π108π109π	104π105σ106π-107π109π110π	96σ103σ105σ-116σ117σ119σ
7 (102)	97π100π102π-103π104π105π	99σ100π102π-103π105π108π	88σ97σ101σ-118σ119σ120σ
8 (110)	105π107π110π-111π112π113π	108σ109σ110π-111π113π116σ	106σ108σ109σ-125σ127σ129σ
9 (97)	94π95π96π-98π99π100π	95σ96π97π-98π100π101π	94σ96σ97σ-106σ110σ112σ
10 (94)	92π93π94π-95π96π97π	91π93π94π-95π97π98σ	86σ87σ90σ-99σ100σ103σ
11 (102)	99π100π102π-103π104π105π	99σ100π102π-103π105π106σ	99σ100σ101σ-106σ111σ112σ
12 (110)	107π108π110π-111π112π113π	107π108π110π-111π113π114σ	107σ108σ109σ-114σ120σ121σ
13 (92)	90σ91π92π-93π94π95π	90π91π92π-93π95π96σ	84σ89σ90σ-96σ98σ107σ
14 (106)	101π104π106π-107π108π109π	104π105σ106π-107π109σ110π	103σ104σ105σ-122σ125σ126σ
15 (114)	108π112π114π-115π116π117π	112π113σ114π-115π118π120π	111σ112σ113σ-131σ133σ134σ
16 (106)	103π104π106π-107π108π109π	103π104π106π-107π109π110σ	96σ103σ105σ-110σ115σ117σ
17 (114)	111π112π114π-115π116π117π	111π112π114π-115π117π118π	103σ110σ113σ-118σ123σ124σ
18 (102)	100π101π102π-103π104π105π	100σ101π102π-103π105π106π	91σ99σ100σ-106σ112σ113σ
19 (110)	106π108π110π-111π112π113π	107σ108π110π-111π113π114π	106σ107σ110σ-119σ120σ121σ
20 (110)	107π108π110π-111π112π113π	107π108π110π-111π113π114π	107σ108σ109σ-114σ119σ120σ
21 (118)	113π116π118π-119π120π121π	115σ116π118π-119π121π122π	106σ114σ117σ-122σ127σ128σ
22 (102)	99π100π102π-103π104π105π	100π101σ102π-103π105π106π	93σ99σ101σ-111σ112σ114σ
23 (106)	101π104π106π-107π108π109π	104π105σ106π-107π109π112σ	102σ103σ105σ-120σ121σ122σ

Results for Group B

Figure 5 shows the common skeleton numbering of Group B used for LMRA.

Figure 5: Common skeleton numbering (Group B)

The best equation obtained is:

$$\log(K_i) = -5.30 + 5.85S_{22}^E(\text{HOMO}-1)^* - 2.15\mu_{20} - 1.48S_2^E(\text{HOMO}-1)^* - 22.68F_9(\text{HOMO}-2)^* \quad (2)$$

with $n=14$, $R=0.99$, $R^2=0.98$, $\text{adj-}R^2=0.97$, $F(4,9)=91.97$ ($p<0.000001$) and a standard error of estimate of 0.17. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the $\pm 2\sigma$ limits. Here, $S_{22}^E(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$ is the electrophilic superdelocalizability of the second highest occupied MO localized on atom 22, μ_{20} is the local atomic electronic chemical potential of atom 20, $S_2^E(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$ is the electrophilic superdelocalizability of the second highest occupied MO localized on atom 2 and $F_9(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$ is the Fukui index of the third occupied MO localized on atom 9. Tables 6 and 7 show the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of variables and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 2. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 7). Figure 6 displays the plot of observed *vs.* calculated $\log(K_i)$.

Table 6: Beta coefficients and t-test for significance of variables in Eq. 2

Variable	Beta	t(9)	p-level
$S_{22}^E(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$	0.65	11.44	0.000001
μ_{20}	-0.43	-7.79	0.00003
$S_2^E(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$	-0.21	-3.92	0.004
$F_9(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$	-0.19	-3.48	0.007

Table 7: Matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables in Eq. 2

	$S_{22}^E(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$	μ_{20}	$S_2^E(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$	$F_9(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$
$S_{22}^E(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$	1.00			
μ_{20}	-0.29	1.00		
$S_2^E(\text{HOMO}-1)^*$	-0.30	0.17	1.00	
$F_9(\text{HOMO}-2)^*$	-0.13	-0.19	0.10	1.00

Figure 6: Plot of predicted versus observed $\log(K_i)$ values (Eq. 2). Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval. The associated statistical parameters of Eq. 2 indicate that this equation is statistically significant and that the variation of the numerical values of a group of four local atomic reactivity indices of atoms of the common skeleton explains about 97% of the variation of $\log(K_i)$. Figure 6, spanning about 3 orders of magnitude, shows that there is a good correlation of observed *versus* calculated values.

Local Molecular Orbitals

Table 8 shows the local molecular orbitals of atoms 2, 9, 20 and 22 (see Fig. 5). Nomenclature: Molecule (HOMO) / (HOMO-2)* (HOMO-1)* (HOMO)* - (LUMO)* (LUMO+1)* (LUMO+2)*.

Table 8: Local Molecular Orbitals of atoms 2, 9, 20 and 22

Molecule	Atom 2	Atom 9	Atom 20	Atom 22
1 (91)	87π89π90π-92π94π95π	89σ90σ91σ-92π94π97π	89π90π91π-92π93π95π	88π89π91π-93π94π95π
2 (95)	91π93π94π-96π97π98π	93σ94π95σ-96π98σ101π	93σ94π95π-96π97π99π	92π93π95π- 97π99π100π
3 (91)	88π89π90π-92π94π95π	89σ90σ91σ-92π93π94σ	89π90σ91π-92π93π95π	88π89π91π-93π94π95π
4 (95)	89π92π93π-96π98π99π	93σ94σ95π-96π98σ99π	92σ93π94π-96π97π99π	92π93π94π-97π98π99π
5 (95)	93π94π95π-96π97π98π	93σ94σ95σ-96π98σ101π	93π94π95π- 97π100π101π	92π93π95π-97π98π99π
6 (102)	98π99π101π-104π105π106π	100π101σ102σ-104π106σ107π	100σ101π102π- 105π107π108π	100π101π102π- 105π107π108π
7 (102)	99π101π102π-103π104π105π	100π101σ102σ-103π104σ106π	100σ101σ102π- 105π108π109π	100π101π102π- 105π106π108π
8 (99)	95π97π98π-100π101π102π	97σ98σ99σ-100π102σ105π	97π98π99π- 100π101π103π	96π97π99π- 101π102π103π
9 (103)	99π101π102π-104π105π106π	101σ102σ103σ-104π106σ109π	101π102π103π- 104π105π107π	100π101π103π- 105π107π108π
10 (99)	96π97π98π-100π101π102π	97σ98σ99σ-100π102σ103π	97π98σ99π- 100π101π103π	96π97π99π- 101π102π103π
11 (103)	96π97π101π-104π105π106π	101σ102σ103π-104π106σ107π	100σ101π102π- 104π105π107π	100π101π102π- 105π106π107π
12 (106)	102π103π105π-108π109π110π	104π105σ106σ-108π110σ111π	104π105σ106π- 109π111π112	104π105π106π- 109π111π112π
13 (108)	102π105π106π-109π110π111π	105σ106σ107σ-109π110π111π	105σ106π107π- 110π112π113π	105π106π107π- 110π111π112π
14 (111)	108π109π110π-112π113π114	109σ110σ111σ- 112π114σ117σ	109σ110σ111π- 112π113π115π	109π110π111π- 113π115π116π
15 (90)	87π88π90π-91π92π93π	88σ89σ90σ-91π93σ95π	87π88π90π-91π92π95π	85π86π90π-92π94π95π

Discussion

Discussion of the results for Group A (Eq. 1).

Table 3 shows that the importance of variables in Eq. 1 is $\varphi_{R_4} > \mu_{21} > F_{10}(\text{HOMO-1})^* > F_5(\text{HOMO-2})^*$. A high receptor affinity is associated with small values for φ_{R_4} , negative values for μ_{21} and small (positive) values for $F_{10}(\text{HOMO-1})^*$ and $F_5(\text{HOMO-2})^*$. A small value for R_4 (Table 1 and Fig. 1) suggests that a hydrogen atom seems to be the best choice for substitution at this site. Atom 21 is the carbon atom attached to N20 (Fig. 3). A high receptor affinity is associated with negative values for μ_{21} . This index is the midpoint between (HOMO)* and (LUMO)* energies. Table 5 shows that all local MOs have a σ nature, that (LUMO)* is energetically far from the molecular LUMO and that (HOMO)* is very close the molecule's HOMO. Therefore, to get more negative values for μ_{21} , we can substitute atom 21 in such a way that the molecule's LUMO or LUMO+1 be localized on this atom. Making the empty MOs more reactive suggests that atom 21 is probably interacting with a site (atom or residue) with occupied σ MOs (sometimes called an apolar region). The best candidates are the methylenic groups of amino acids. Atom 10 is a carbon atom in ring B (Fig. 3). A high affinity is associated with small values for $F_{10}(\text{HOMO-1})^*$. Table 5 shows that the local frontier MOs coincide with the molecule's frontier MOs and that all they have a π nature. This suggests that the first three highest occupied local MOs of atom 10 should correspond to inner occupied MOs of the molecule. This, in turn, suggests that atom 10 is employing its empty local MOs to interact with an electron-rich center. Atom 5 is a carbon atom shared by rings A and B (Fig. 3). Table 5 shows that $(\text{HOMO-2})_5^*$ may have a σ or π natures. Considering that a high receptor affinity is associated with small values for $F_5(\text{HOMO-2})^*$ the analysis is

similar to the one presented for atom 10. Therefore, we suggest that atom 5 is interacting with an electron-rich center. All the suggestions are displayed in the partial 2D pharmacophore of Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Partial 2D pharmacophore for CBR receptor affinity

Discussion of the results for Group B

Table 6 shows that the importance of variables in Eq. 2 is $S_{22}^E(\text{HOMO-1})^* > \mu_{20} > S_2^E(\text{HOMO-1})^* > F_9(\text{HOMO-2})^*$. A high receptor affinity is associated with high (negative) values for $S_{22}^E(\text{HOMO-1})^*$, small (negative) values for μ_{20} , small (negative) values for $S_2^E(\text{HOMO-1})^*$ and high values for $F_9(\text{HOMO-2})^*$. Atom 22 is the oxygen atom (see Fig. 5, atom 22 is a nitrogen atom in the case of molecule 15, Table 2). Table 8 shows that the three highest occupied and the three lowest empty MOs have a π nature and that in almost all molecules the local HOMO* coincides with the molecule's HOMO. High negative values for $S_{22}^E(\text{HOMO-1})^*$ are obtained by shifting upwards the MO energy, making this MO more reactive. Therefore, we suggest that atom 22 is interacting with an electron-deficient center through at least its first two highest occupied local MOs. Atom 20 is a nitrogen atom in ring C (Fig. 5). Table 8 shows that the highest occupied local MO coincides with the molecule's HOMO or HOMO-1. The lowest empty local MO coincides with the molecule's LUMO, LUMO+1 or LUMO+2. Both local MOs have a π nature. A high receptor affinity is associated with small (negative) values for μ_{20} . This means that the midpoint of the HOMO*-LUMO* energy must be shifted upwards. This can be achieved by shifting upwards the energy of the LUMO*. Therefore, the empty MOs become less reactive. Another way is shifting upwards the energy of the local HOMO* (if possible) making it more reactive. Within this idea, we suggest that atom 20 is interacting with an electron-deficient center. Atom 2 is a carbon atom in ring A (Fig. 5). A high receptor affinity is associated with small (negative) values for $S_2^E(\text{HOMO-1})^*$. Table 8 shows that the three highest occupied and the three lowest empty MOs have a π nature. Small negative values are obtained by making more negative the $(\text{HOMO-1})_2^*$ energy, making this MO less reactive. This suggests that atom 2 is interacting with an electron-rich center. Atom 9 is a carbon atom in ring B (Fig. 5). A high receptor affinity is associated with high values for $F_9(\text{HOMO-2})^*$. This is indicative of an interaction of atom 9 with at least one electron-deficient center. All the suggestions are displayed in the partial 2D pharmacophore of Fig. 8.

Figure 8: Partial 2D pharmacophore for CBR receptor affinity

In conclusion, for the two sets of molecules we have obtained good correlations between the variation of the CBR binding affinity and the variation of the numerical values of local atomic reactivity indices (and orientational parameters) for a definite set of atoms. This should help the experimentalist to search for more active molecules.

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